

Title:**An electroluminescent and tunable cavity enhanced carbon-nanotube-emitter in the telecom band**

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Motivation and Description of the work:

Emerging photonic information processing systems require chip-level integration of controllable nanoscale light sources at telecommunication wavelengths. Currently, substantial challenges remain in the dynamic control of the sources, the low-loss integration into a photonic environment, and in the site-selective placement at desired positions on a chip. We overcome these challenges using heterogeneous integration of electroluminescent (EL), semiconducting carbon nanotubes (sCNTs) into hybrid 2d-3d photonic circuits. We demonstrate enhanced spectral line shaping of the EL sCNT emission. By back-gating the sCNT-nanoemitter we achieve full on-chip electrical dynamic control of the EL sCNT emission with high on-off ratio and strong enhancement in the telecommunication band. Using nanographene as a low-loss material to electrically contact sCNT emitters directly within a photonic crystal cavity enables highly efficient EL coupling without compromising the optical quality of the cavity. Our integrated hybrid approach allows to redirect the enhanced EL signal propagating in a photonic waveguide to 3D polymer couplers for convenient out of plane optical read-out. Our versatile procedure of site-selective placement of electroluminescent sCNT emitters in custom-designed low-loss nanographene-photonic environments with high fidelity and reproducibility paves the way for controllable integrated photonic circuits on chip.

EL spectroscopy measurement setup

The fabricated chip is mounted on a custom-made sample holder and placed into sample-in-vacuum optical cryostat system. The devices are electrically connected onto palladium pads attached to the sample holder by means of wire bonding. Devices are electrically driven by an Agilent 4155B semiconductor parameter analyzer. Constant-current biasing is applied on source and drain electrodes through separate source-measurement units (SMU) and a third SMU is used for gate voltage while the drain electrode is set as reference. The optical access to the sample is through a 0.5 mm thick quartz window with an Olympus LMPLN 10XIR objective mounted on a customized Zeiss Axiotech Vario microscope. The emitted light is focused into an imaging spectrograph (Acton SP-2360, Princeton Instruments) and onto an InGaAs photodiode linear array (PyLoN-IR, Princeton Instruments) with 1024 pixels, sensitive from 950 to 1610 nm. The xy position of the sample is controlled with sub- μm precision by a motorized scanning stage (8MTF, Standa), and the z-axis working distance is adjusted by a high-precision objective positioner (P-721 PIFOC/E-665 piezo scanner, Physics Instruments), which allowed precise and stable positioning of the emitter.

Data types and formats: Files are downloaded in the format of .opj